

ON SMARANDACHE ALGEBRAIC STRUCTURES.
III : THE COMMUTATIVE RING $B(a,n)$

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Abstract In this paper we construct a class of commutative rings under the Smarandache algorithm.

Key words . Smarandache algorithm , commutative ring .

Let a, n be integers such that $a \neq 0$ and $n > 1$. Under the definitions and notions in [1], let

$$(1) \quad B(a,n) = \begin{cases} \{0, 1, a, \dots, a^{f-1}\} \pmod{n}, & \text{if } l=1, \\ \{0, a, a^2, \dots, a^{e+f-1}\} \pmod{n}, & \text{if } l > 1. \end{cases}$$

In this paper we prove the following result.

Theorem . If m is a prime and a is a primitive root modulo m , then $B(a,n)$ is a commutative ring under the Smarandache additive and multiplicative.

Proof . Since $B(a,n) = A(a,n) \cup \{0\}$ by (1) , $B(a,n)$ is a commutative multiplicative semigroup under the Smarandache algorithm (see [2]).

Notice that m is a prime and a is a primitive root modulo m . Then we have $f = m - 1$. If $l = 1$, then $B(a,n) = \{0, 1, 2, \dots, m-1\} \pmod{m}$. Therefore , $B(a,n)$ is a commutative additive group . It implies that $B(a,n)$ is a commutative ring under additive and multiplicative . If $l > 1$, since $l \mid a^e$, then from (1) we see that $B(a,n) = \{0, l, 2l, \dots, (m-1)l\} \pmod{n}$. Therefore , $B(a,n)$ is also a commutative ring . The theorem is proved .

References

- [1] M.-H. Le , On Smarandache algebraic structures I: The commutative multiplicative semigroup $A(a,n)$, Smarandache Notions J., 12(2001).
- [2] R.Padilla , Smarandache algebraic structures , Smarandache Notions J. 9(1998),36-38.

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